

University of Novi Sad
**INSTITUTE
OF FOOD
TECHNOLOGY
IN NOVI SAD**

feed
congress

16-18 October, 2024
Novi Sad, Serbia

5th

**INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS
FOOD TECHNOLOGY,
QUALITY AND SAFETY**

e-ABSTRACT BOOK

ISBN 978-86-7994-063-6

V INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS “FOOD TECHNOLOGY, QUALITY AND SAFETY”, 16-18 OCTOBER 2024, NOVI SAD, REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

Publisher

University of Novi Sad
Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad
Bulevar cara Lazara 1
21000 Novi Sad
Republic of Serbia

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- Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia
- Provincial Secretariat for Agriculture, Water Management and Forestry, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia
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CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

663/664:658.562(048.3)
614.31(048.3)

INTERNATIONAL Congress "Food Technology, Quality and Safety" (5 ; 2024 ; Novi Sad)

e-Abstract book [Elektronski izvor] / 5th International Congress "Food Technology, Quality and Safety", 16-18 October 2024, Novi Sad ; [main editor Ljubiša Šarić]. - Novi Sad : Institute of Food Technology, 2024

Način pristupa (URL): https://fins.uns.ac.rs/publications/?_sft_publicationss=zbornik. - Opis zasnovan na stanju na dan 22.10.2024.

ISBN 978-86-7994-063-6

а) Животне намирнице -- Контрола квалитета -- Апстракти б) Животне намирнице -- Хигијена -- Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 155106313

FOODS AND BEVERAGES CONTAINERS AS POTENTIAL SOURCES OF BISPHENOL A – SURVEY AMONG LUNG CANCER PATIENTS

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Lung cancer remains the leading cause of cancer death worldwide, despite the decreasing rates of tobacco smoking. Therefore, there is a noticeable rise of clinical interest in other modifiable risk factors for lung cancer such as alcohol consumption, lack of physical activity, diet, infections and environmental pollution, especially among non-smokers. Bisphenol A (BPA), an endocrine disruptor and environmental pollutant can be found in epoxy resins of food and beverage containers and can leach under normal conditions into the food. BPA enhances the carcinogenesis susceptibility and stimulates in vitro migration and invasion of lung cancer cells. The aim of this study was to evaluate the potential BPA exposure from instant soups, canned food and plastic containers among lung cancer patients. A total of 205 patients out of which 60 (45% female) with small cell lung cancer (SCLC) and 145 (46.21% female) with non-small cell III/IV stage lung cancer (NSCLC) from the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia were surveyed about selected dietary and lifestyle habits. There were no statistical differences in smoking habits among SCLC and NSCLC groups nor between sexes. The use of bagged instant soups and canned foods was the same across SCLC and NSCLC patients ($p=0.314$ and $p=0.177$, respectively). Male patients with SCLC were more frequently users of canned foods in comparison to females ($p=0.010$), with no differences among other types of cancer between genders. The majority of the respondents in both, the SCLC and NSCLC group never used plastic containers for heating foods ($p=0.339$). Despite tobacco smoking is recognized as the main cause of SCLC type, other factors such as the presence of environmental pollutant BPA should also be considered a major health concern. There is an urgent need for the assessment of BPA presence in biological samples of lung cancer patients.

Keywords: lung cancer, bisphenol A, bagged instant soup, canned foods, plastic containers

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research, AP Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia (Grant No. 142-451-3509/2023-01).